

Research Paper

Dexamethasone abolishes intra-day fluctuations of electrode impedance in cochlear implant users

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Dexamethasone-eluting cochlear implant (CI) electrode arrays aim to reduce mean electrode impedance and enhance stability. However, longitudinal data on intra-day impedance dynamics are lacking. This study compared postoperative impedance profiles between users of dexamethasone-eluting FLEX28 (DEX) and conventional FLEX28 (NoDEX) electrodes, focusing on mean impedance levels and intra-day fluctuations.

Methods: Participants were assigned to DEX or NoDEX groups based on electrode type. Both groups measured impedance twice daily (morning and evening) for four months postoperatively via an app. Primary outcomes were mean impedance levels and intra-day fluctuations, represented by the morning-to-evening difference (MED). Analyses were conducted descriptively and by group comparisons using the start of electrical stimulation (t_0) as reference. Four postoperative phases were examined: early postoperative (days 1-10), late postoperative (day 11- t_0), intensive fitting (t_0 -day 21), and regular hearing phase (day 22-4 months).

Results: The DEX group exhibited consistently low and stable impedance values throughout, with no detectable effect of the start of electrical stimulation (t_0). Daily impedance was consistently lower in DEX than in NoDEX, but the differences reached high statistical significance from the late postoperative phase onward ($p < 0.0001$). Intra-day fluctuations were abolished in DEX (MED ≈ 0), whereas NoDEX showed measurable fluctuations during intensive fitting (DEX: 0.0 k Ω , $n = 7$ vs. NoDEX: 0.75 k Ω , $n = 11$; $p < 0.001$) and regular hearing phase (DEX: 0.0 k Ω , $n = 8$ vs. NoDEX: 0.56 k Ω , $n = 11$; $p = 0.02$).

Conclusion: Dexamethasone-eluting FLEX28 electrodes not only reduce mean impedance but also maintain stable values over time and effectively abolish intra-day fluctuations.

1. Introduction

Cochlear implants (CI) are increasingly used in individuals with significant residual natural hearing making atraumatic implantation essential to preserve this residual hearing (Gantz et al., 2022). Modern surgical techniques have been developed that emphasize hearing preservation (Tarabichi et al., 2021; Topsakal et al., 2022). However, cochlear implantation inevitably requires opening a highly specialized and secluded organ with a distinct structural and molecular organization and inserting a foreign body (Furness, 2019; Glueckert et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2017; Nin et al., 2016; Peeleman et al., 2020). Consequently, cochlear tissues are confronted with multiple stimuli for inflammatory

responses (Rahman et al., 2022; Seyyedi and Nadol, 2014).

The two main inflammatory triggers after cochlear implantation are surgical trauma and foreign body reaction towards the electrode. Immediately after insertion, the electrode becomes covered with proteins present in the scala tympani (Anderson et al., 2008; Newbold et al., 2010). This process, which increases polarization impedance and is modulated by electrical stimulation (Bas et al., 2015; Kel et al., 2013; Newbold et al., 2010), facilitates subsequent cellular attachment (Anderson et al., 2008) and thereby contributes to rising access resistance (Kel et al., 2013; Newbold et al., 2010).

During the first postoperative week, pro-inflammatory responses predominate: resident macrophages become activated, additional

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monocytes and leukocytes infiltrate the cochlea (Bas et al., 2015; Kel et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2018; Noonan et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2023), and fibrocytes attach to the electrode surface (Kel et al., 2013). Subsequently, the M2 macrophage-associated healing phase begins, leading to cellular proliferation, differentiation and fibrous encapsulation of the electrode (Bas et al., 2015; Claussen et al., 2022; Okayasu et al., 2020).

Inflammatory reactions are essential for tissue repair and functional recovery (Eming et al., 2007). Foreign bodies that cannot be degraded, are integrated into surrounding tissue via cellular and extracellular matrix structures (Capuani et al., 2022; Carnicer-Lombarte et al., 2021; Noslakovicova et al., 2021). Therefore, some degree of inflammation and fibrous tissue formation is inevitable and physiologically necessary (Gearardyn et al., 2023; Ishai et al., 2017; Nadol et al., 2008). However, strong early inflammatory responses are associated with a more pronounced foreign body reaction and potentially reduced CI performance (Claussen et al., 2022; Gao and Yi, 2022; Kamakura and Nadol, 2016; Seyyedi and Nadol, 2014). Prolonged or reactivated inflammation may further exacerbate these effects, contributing to delayed hearing loss (Gao and Yi, 2022; Kuthubutheen et al., 2016; Neuburger et al., 2009).

Dexamethasone is widely used in otolaryngology for its anti-inflammatory properties (Meltser and Canlon, 2011; Skarzyńska et al., 2022). It is a strong agonist of the glucocorticoid receptor which is widely expressed in the cochlea (Karssen and de, 2007; Kil and Kalinec, 2013; Rarey and Curtis, 1996; Matsui et al., 2023). Generally, its role is in protecting tissue homeostasis under stress (Ferrara et al., 2019). It induces anti-proliferative and anti-inflammatory responses mediated through both genomic and non-genomic mechanisms (Petta et al., 2016; Scheschowitsch et al., 2017). In animal models, dexamethasone-eluting electrode arrays have been shown to modulate the expression of various genes involved in cochlear homeostasis (Takumi et al., 2014). It could also be shown that those electrodes ameliorate the inflammatory responses to insertion trauma (Farhadi et al., 2013; Rahman et al., 2025), as well as the foreign body response after cochlear implantation (Bas et al., 2016; Manrique-Huarte et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2025; Toulemonde et al., 2021; Wilk et al., 2016) and elevated electrode impedance levels (Bas et al., 2016; Fleet et al., 2024; Manrique-Huarte et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2025; Usami et al., 2025; Wilk et al., 2016).

The CIDEXEL developed by MED-EL (Innsbruck, Austria) (Prenzler et al., 2025) incorporates a modified electrode array which is designed to elute intracochlear dexamethasone over a sustained period. The drug is embedded within silicone coatings positioned between the electrode contacts and is gradually eluted following implantation. A prior feasibility study with the CIDEXEL demonstrated its safety and tolerability (Prenzler et al., 2025) and reported significantly lower impedance levels in the study subjects compared with impedances from conventional electrode arrays. In that study, electrode impedance was measured during study visits at the clinic, using clinical software and at pre-scheduled post-operative follow-up visits, which were aligned to the typical pattern and frequency of clinical routine visits.

In our previous study, participants performed twice-daily self-measurements of impedance levels using a smartphone app (Vormelcher et al., 2025). This permitted high-density measurement, with a temporal resolution far beyond that of routine clinical follow-up. We introduced this measurement paradigm in a cohort of users implanted with conventional electrode arrays (Vormelcher et al., 2025). Among other observations, we found that conventional arrays exhibit marked intra-day fluctuations in impedance levels, with higher levels in the morning and lower levels in the evening as soon as electrical stimulation is present. Such patterns would be difficult to detect using standard clinical follow-up schedules, but were clearly revealed by high-density self-measurement.

In the present study, we compared the longitudinal changes in self-measured impedance levels between dexamethasone-eluting and conventional FLEX28 electrode arrays. Both groups self-measured electrode impedance twice daily (morning and evening) over a period of four months postoperatively. The primary goal was to compare the intra-day

fluctuations in impedance levels across the two electrode array types. We hypothesized that dexamethasone administration would attenuate the development of an impedance increase, promote overall impedance stability, and reduce variability including intra-day fluctuations.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Ethics and informed consent

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki by the World Medical Association and received approval from the local ethics committee at Hannover Medical School (reference numbers: 911_5BO_S_2020 and 9115_BO_S_2022). All participants were fully informed about the study procedures and provided their explicit written consent prior to participation.

2.2. Study design, inclusion criteria, and participant details

This analysis was based on data from a prospective, monocentric study conducted at the German Hearing Center of the Hannover Medical School. The study commenced in June 2020, with the final participant completing the four-month postoperative follow-up in August 2023.

The study design, setting, and inclusion criteria were identical to those described in the initial publications reporting app-based daily self-measurement of impedance (Vormelcher et al., 2025) and the feasibility study of the CIDEXEL (Prenzler et al., 2025) and the present cohort includes a subset of the patients previously reported in those studies. Briefly, participants were eligible if they met the following criteria:

- Age ≥ 18 years
- Normal inner ear anatomy
- First cochlear implantation in the ear to be measured
- Use of a MED-EL SONNET2 audio processor
- Willingness to use a smartphone
- Residency in Germany
- Proficiency in German to understand study procedures and provide informed consent

A total of 22 participants (14 male and 8 female) were analyzed. Detailed demographic information for each participant is provided in Supplementary Table S1. Nine participants were implanted with a dexamethasone-eluting FLEX28 electrode array (Prenzler et al., 2025) while 13 participants were implanted with a conventional FLEX28 electrode array (MED-EL, Innsbruck, Austria).

2.3. Study procedure

Participants were assigned to one of two groups, termed DEX and NoDEX, based on the FLEX28 variant used. During the initial post-operative implant check, typically one to three days after surgery, the Telemetry App was provided to all participants. The Telemetry App is a research software developed by MED-EL. For technical details, we refer to our previous publication (Vormelcher et al., 2025). Briefly, the Telemetry App enables participants to perform self-measurements of electrode impedance via a smartphone connection to their audio processor. When a measurement session is initiated, impedance is measured separately on all twelve electrode contacts.

All participants were trained by the study team in how to use the Telemetry App during the postoperative implant check, where the first impedance measurement was conducted. Following this supervised session, participants were instructed to independently perform measurements at home. They were asked to measure impedances twice daily: once in the morning after attaching the audio processor and once in the evening before removing it.

This measurement schedule was to be followed consistently for a

duration of four months post-implantation. For all participants, no electrical stimulation was applied until the intensive fitting week, taking place approximately 4 weeks after surgery. Nevertheless, participants were instructed to carry out measurements during the pre-fitting interval.

2.4. App impedance measurements

2.4.1. Time allocation of measurements

App measurements were categorized as morning (04:00 a.m. to 12:59 p.m.) or evening (04:00 p.m. to 01:59 a.m.). Measurements outside these time windows were excluded. If more than one morning or evening measurement was made on the same day, only the first morning and the last evening measurement were retained. The initial measurement performed during the postoperative implant check was classified as a morning entry, regardless of the actual time.

Intensive fitting did not always begin exactly 4 weeks after surgery (Supplementary Figure S3). To improve comparability, we indexed all measurement times from the first day of intensive fitting (t_0) rather than from the day of implantation. Data were analyzed for up to 30 days prior to t_0 and for up to 4 months postoperatively. The study period was divided into four phases:

- *Early postoperative* (the first ten days after implantation)
- *Late postoperative* (from the eleventh day after implantation to t_0)
- *Intensive fitting* (from t_0 to day $t_0 + 21$)
- *Regular hearing* (from day $t_0 + 22$ to 4 months post-op)

As stated above, the reference point (t_0) reflects the start of the intensive fitting week, when both groups received their initial electrical stimulation.

2.4.2. Analysis of impedance measurements

The Telemetry App measures total impedance values comparable to the clinical MAESTRO software (MED-EL). Channels with a status other than OK or disabled channels were excluded and treated as missing data. The average impedance across valid channels (C1–C12) was computed separately for morning and evening measurements. Following the same approach as described in our previous study (Vormelcher et al., 2025), only participants with an app usage rate of at least 33 % of all possible days within the observation period were included in the longitudinal impedance analysis. Analyses were performed using Python version 3.11.9 with the libraries pandas, numpy, matplotlib, seaborn, scipy, and statannotations.

2.4.3. Morning-to-evening differences in impedance

Within-participant morning-to-evening differences (MED) in impedance were calculated for each postoperative phase. MED was defined as the morning impedance minus the evening impedance and is used as a measure of intra-day fluctuation.

2.5. Statistical analysis

To ensure the validity of the statistical tests, outliers in the mean impedance values were identified by computing the interquartile range (IQR) separately for each group and each postoperative phase. Extreme outliers were defined as values exceeding $3 \times$ IQR and these values were excluded from analysis to minimize the influence of participant-specific effects.

The main comparisons focused on differences between the two electrode array groups within each phase. Normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test, and the equality of variance was assessed using Levene's test. Both tests were performed separately for the data within each phase. Depending on these results, we either used the Mann-Whitney U test (MWU) or Welch's t-test to assess the significance of differences between the groups. In the Results section, we specify which

test was used for each comparison.

The significance threshold was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. To adjust for multiple comparisons, the Bonferroni correction was applied.

3. Results

3.1. Participant inclusion, app compliance, and outlier analysis

Participants with an app usage rate greater than 33 % were assigned an identifier (ID #, Supplementary Table S1), which is used for the individual impedance representations throughout the manuscript. Of the $n = 22$ participants, $n = 19$ had an app usage rate eligible for the longitudinal impedance analysis ($n = 8$ DEX; $n = 11$ NoDEX, Supplementary Figure S1).

Supplementary Table S2 summarizes the number and percentage of removed values for the DEX and NoDEX groups. Extreme outliers occurred only during the early and late postoperative phases. No participant had their complete data excluded. A sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess whether the $3 \times$ IQR exclusion criterion affected the statistical outcomes, and the corresponding analyses including the raw values are provided in Supplementary Figure S2. These results show that the impedance trajectories and group-level patterns remain consistent when all outliers are retained, and the statistical outcomes regarding the group differences remain statistically significant.

3.2. Impedance measurements across time

The means and standard deviations of impedance values averaged across all valid channels (C1–C12) over time are shown separately for each group in Fig. 1 A (morning) and Fig. 2 A (evening). Summary distributions of impedance values averaged across all valid channels (C1–C12) stratified by postoperative phases are shown separately for each group in Fig. 1 B (morning) and Fig. 2 B (evening).

Individual participant measurements averaged across all valid channels are shown in Supplementary Figure S3. Here the individual data are indexed to the date of implantation rather than to the start of the intensive fitting week, as used in our main analysis.

3.2.1. Morning impedance measurements

In the early postoperative phase, mean impedance in NoDEX group rapidly increased, while that in the DEX group slightly decreased (Fig. 1 A). During the late postoperative phase, mean impedance values were stable within both groups, with lower values in the DEX group (DEX: 3.09 ± 0.57 k Ω , $n = 7$; NoDEX: 7.97 ± 0.68 k Ω , $n = 11$).

With the onset of electrical stimulation at the beginning of the intensive fitting week, a rapid decline in mean impedance was observed in the NoDEX group. The great majority of this decline occurred within the first day of the intensive fitting week, thus corresponding to the onset of stimulation. The magnitude of the decline was > 1.8 k Ω , corresponding to a decrease of -21.9 % between day -1 to day 1.

A small increase in mean impedance was observed in the DEX group with the onset of stimulation. The magnitude was < 0.2 k Ω , corresponding to a slight increase of 6.8 % between day -1 to day 1. The mean impedance in the DEX group remained considerably lower than in the NoDEX group at the end of the intensive fitting week (day 4: DEX: 3.21 ± 0.76 k Ω , $n = 7$; NoDEX: 6.08 ± 0.57 k Ω , $n = 10$). During the regular hearing phase there was mean difference in morning impedance of approximately 2.8 k Ω between the groups.

Fig. 1 B shows summary distributions of the morning measurements within each phase, stratified by group. Mean impedance was significantly lower in the DEX group during all phases (Table 1). The MWU test was used for the early postoperative phase comparison due to the skewed distributions in both groups (Fig. 1 A and B).

3.2.2. Evening impedance measurements

The longitudinal evening measurements are shown in Fig. 2 A. In

Fig. 1. (A) Daily mean morning impedance (kΩ) measured with the Telemetry App for DEX group (dotted red line) and NoDEX group (solid blue line). Shaded areas represent the standard deviation. Vertical lines mark the postoperative phases. The period 30–22 days before t_0 includes mixed data from both the early and late postoperative phases. (B) Summary distributions of impedance values for the DEX and NoDEX groups measured in the morning, stratified by postoperative phases. Boxes show interquartile ranges with medians and means (dashed line); whiskers depict min/max values. T-test with Bonferroni correction (**** $p \leq 0.0001$, * $0.01 < p \leq 0.05$).

Fig. 2. (A) Daily mean evening impedance (kΩ) measured with the Telemetry App for DEX group (dotted red line) and NoDEX group (solid blue line). Shaded areas represent the standard deviation. Vertical lines mark the postoperative phases. The period 30–22 days before t_0 includes mixed data from both the early and late postoperative phases. (B) Summary distributions of impedance values for the DEX and NoDEX groups measured in the evening, stratified by postoperative phases. Boxes show interquartile ranges with medians and means (dashed line); whiskers depict min/max values. T-test with Bonferroni correction (**** $p \leq 0.0001$, *** $0.0001 < p \leq 0.001$).

Table 1

Comparison of the morning impedances in the DEX and NoDEX groups at each postoperative phase. The mean impedance values are shown. Note: DEX - $n = 7$ in the late postoperative phase, $n = 8$ in all other conditions; NoDEX - $n = 10$ in the early postoperative phase, $n = 11$ in all other conditions.

Phase	DEX		NoDEX		p-value	
	Mean morning impedance (kΩ)	SD	Mean morning impedance (kΩ)	SD	MWU	t-test
Early Postoperative	3.36		5.91		0.03	
Late Postoperative	3.09		7.97			<0.0001
Intensive Fitting	3.20		6.41			<0.0001
Regular Hearing	2.99		5.79			<0.0001

both groups, the trends observed were quite similar to the morning measurements. A reduction in mean impedance coincided with the onset of stimulation in the NoDEX group. The magnitude was > 2 kΩ, corresponding to a reduction of -26.4 % between day -1 and day 1.

In the DEX group, mean values were consistently low throughout the study period. At the onset of stimulation there was a minor reduction of < 0.3 kΩ, (-9.2 % between day -1 and day 1).

Fig. 2 B shows summary distributions of the evening measurements within each phase, stratified by group. Mean impedance was significantly lower in the DEX group during all phases (Table 2). As with the morning values, the MWU test was used for the early postoperative phase comparison.

3.3. Morning-to-evening differences in impedance

After the onset of stimulation in the NoDEX group, mean impedance was consistently lower for evening measurements compared to morning measurements (Figs. 1 B and 2 B). We further quantified this by calculating the MED.

Fig. 3 A shows the distribution of MED values over time for each group. In both groups, the mean MED was close to zero during the early and late postoperative phases (late postop: DEX: -0.03 ± 0.06 k Ω , $n = 7$; NoDEX: 0.04 ± 0.12 k Ω , $n = 11$).

With the onset of stimulation, there was an abrupt increase in mean MED in the NoDEX group (intensive fitting phase: 0.75 ± 0.73 k Ω , $n = 11$). While mean values are generally reported, intra-day fluctuations of up to 2.4 k Ω were observed in individual patients on some measurement days after the onset of electrical stimulation. The initial rapid rise in mean MED in the NoDEX group was followed by an equally abrupt decline, reaching a steady state of approximately 0.5 k Ω , which was sustained throughout the regular hearing phase.

In the DEX group, no increase in mean MED occurred with the onset of stimulation (intensive fitting phase: DEX: 0.0 ± 0.06 k Ω , $n = 7$). Mean MED remained consistently low throughout the regular hearing phase. The inter-individual variance was also markedly lower compared to the NoDEX group (Fig. 3 A).

Fig. 3 B shows summary distributions of the MED values within each phase, stratified by group. There were no significant differences in MED between the groups within the early or late postoperative phases (Table 3). Significant differences were observed between the groups in the intensive fitting and regular hearing phases.

A comparison of the MED across cochlear regions (apical, medial, and basal) within each postoperative phase is presented in Supplementary Figure S4.

4. Discussion

4.1. Data collection limitations

Participants were instructed to perform their morning measurement immediately after connecting their processor for the first time that day. However, we cannot be certain this was always done. The Telemetry App records only the measurement time, not the processor activation time. As such, it is possible that some users performed their morning measurement after using the processor for some time. This might explain why morning impedance was consistently, but not universally, higher than evening impedance (Supplementary Figure S3). Similar variability in user behavior has been reported by Khan et al., who observed that remote impedance checks were often performed at inconsistent times of day, leading to differing amounts of stimulation prior to measurement (Khan et al., 2026). This further supports the likelihood that variable processor-use durations contributed to the intra-day differences seen in our study. Automating the measurement process could help reduce this uncertainty, for example by triggering an initial reading immediately

Table 2

Comparison of the evening impedances in the DEX and NoDEX groups at each postoperative phase. The mean impedance values are shown. Note: DEX - $n = 6$ in the early postoperative, $n = 7$ in the late postoperative phase and $n = 8$ in all other conditions; NoDEX - $n = 10$ in the early postoperative phase and $n = 11$ in all other conditions.

Phase	DEX Mean evening impedance (k Ω)	NoDEX Mean evening impedance (k Ω)	p-value	
			MWU	t-test
Early Postoperative	3.31	5.93	0.001	
Late Postoperative	3.39	7.87		<0.0001
Intensive Fitting	3.25	5.65		<0.0001
Regular Hearing	3.08	5.20		<0.0001

upon the first processor activation of the day.

Despite a relatively high overall usage rate of 68 % across the 4-month observation period (Supplementary Figure S1), data collection was not consistent for all participants. Some had large gaps in their measurements, particularly during the pre-stimulation phases (Supplementary Figure S3). This is a common challenge in longitudinal studies relying on self-measurement (Vormelcher et al., 2025). Missing assessments must be considered when interpreting these longitudinal trends, particularly in this small cohort where individual compliance can disproportionately influence group-level analyses. To rule out the possibility that fluctuations in participant numbers could create artificial peaks or troughs in the averaged impedance values, we performed a leave-one-out jackknife analysis. For both morning and evening data, statistical significance was unchanged when any single participant was removed, indicating that the results are robust and not driven by variations in participant availability (Supplementary Table S3, S4).

As outlined in our previous publication, evening impedance measurements via the app are preferable for comparisons with routine impedance and field telemetry (IFT) measurements, as both are obtained following a period of electrical stimulation (Vormelcher et al., 2025). The mean IFT values of the DEX group, previously reported by Prenzler et al. (Prenzler et al., 2025), closely align with the mean evening impedance values observed in the DEX group of the present study (IFT at 3-month clinical follow-up: 3.12 ± 0.54 k Ω , $n = 9$; impedance measured via Telemetry App during the regular hearing phase: 3.08 k $\Omega \pm 0.5$ k Ω , $n = 8$).

4.2. Impedance development without dexamethasone

The mean impedance in the NoDEX group during the early and late postoperative phase (Figs. 1 A and 2 A) corresponded well with the trajectories for cochlear healing phases generally reported in the literature. A rapid increase is seen in the first days after implantation, followed by stabilization at this higher level prior to the onset of electrical stimulation (Bas et al., 2016; Claussen et al., 2022; Kel et al., 2013). In our study, morning and evening impedance was comparable prior initiation of electrical stimulation.

Once stimulation was initiated, mean impedance decreased for both morning (-1.79 k Ω , -21.9 %) and evening (-2.14 k Ω , -26.4 %) measurements. Fluctuations between morning and evening values were observed, with evening measurements consistently lower in mean impedance. In the longer term, mean impedance values and MED decreased slowly over time; however, a positive MED continued to reflect ongoing daily impedance fluctuations (MED during regular hearing phase: 0.56 k Ω). The comparison of MED across different cochlear regions (apical, medial, and basal) revealed a pattern similar to that observed when averaging across all electrode contacts (Supplementary Figure S4), with the highest MED values consistently occurring in the apical region. Evening impedance values averaged across all electrode contacts decreased by approximately 8 % over the study period (from 5.65 k Ω to 5.20 k Ω), which is in accord with literature reports (Paasche et al., 2009).

4.3. Biological processes underlying impedance

Generally, the drop of impedance with the onset of stimulation was higher than the daily fluctuations between morning and evening levels. These observed impedance dynamics may reflect the contribution of distinct intracochlear processes that drive both longer-lasting and short-term reversible impedance changes. We propose that two components may underlie these dynamics:

1. A longer-lasting, stimulation-dependent component, reflected in the lower impedance level that establishes after the onset of electrical stimulation. While this level remains relatively stable during continuous daily use, it is known to increase again when stimulation

Fig. 3. (A) Daily mean morning-to-evening differences in impedance (MED; kΩ, morning-evening) measured with the Telemetry App for DEX group (dotted red line) and NoDEX group (solid blue line). Shaded areas represent standard deviation. The reference point (t_0) is the start of the intensive fitting week. The period 30–22 days before t_0 includes mixed data from both the early and late postoperative phases. (B) Distributions of MED (kΩ) for the DEX and NoDEX groups within the postoperative phases. Boxes show interquartile ranges with medians and means (dashed line); whiskers depict min/max values. T-test with Bonferroni correction (** $0.0001 < p \leq 0.001$; * $0.01 < p \leq 0.05$; ns: $p > 0.05$).

Table 3

Comparison of MED values between the DEX and NoDEX groups at each postoperative phase. The mean morning-to-evening differences are shown. Note: DEX - $n = 7$ in the early, late postoperative and intensive fitting phase, $n = 8$ in the regular hearing phase; NoDEX - $n = 10$ in the early postoperative phase, $n = 11$ in all other conditions.

Phase	DEX		NoDEX		p-value	
	Mean MED (kΩ)	SD	Mean MED (kΩ)	SD	MWU	t-test
Early Postoperative	-0.05	0.05	-0.21	0.05	0.13	
Late Postoperative	-0.03	0.05	0.04	0.05		0.97
Intensive Fitting	0.00	0.05	0.75	0.05		<0.001
Regular Hearing	0.00	0.05	0.56	0.05		0.02

is discontinued for extended periods. Thus, it represents a semi-stable baseline that depends on ongoing stimulation rather than a fully persistent biological state.

2. A short-term reversible component, indicated by the systematic morning-to-evening differences after stimulation, is introduced. These fluctuations likely arise from transient electrochemical or biological processes that recover overnight and diminish during the course of daily stimulation.

Differentiation between biological responses at the electrode-tissue interface or electro-chemical conductivity at the electrode-electrolyte interface and their contribution to permanent and reversible impedance changes could not be made here. Further studies are needed to investigate the associations between daily impedance fluctuations and intracochlear processes, preferably through the analysis of impedance subcomponents (Oliveira et al., 2025; Schraivogel et al., 2023).

4.4. Impact of stimulation on cochlear microenvironment

The decline in impedance with the onset of stimulation (and with the resumption of stimulation after a rest period) is in line with published *in vivo* and *in vitro* data (Newbold et al., 2004; Newbold et al., 2014). Generally, changes in impedance could be due to stimulation induced longer-lasting modification of the surrounding tissues. Electrical stimulation does influence cellular proliferation and differentiation (Meng et al., 2021), however immune response within the cochlea might differ

from other tissues (Hu et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2018). There is evidence that fibrous encapsulation is increased near electrode contacts in human (Ishai et al., 2017; Jensen et al., 2022) and a positive influence on fibrotic encapsulation of electrical stimulation under pro-inflammatory conditions has been shown *in vitro* (Zhang et al., 2023). Although clear evidence for electrical stimulation influencing tissue growth and organization could not be established *in vitro* (Rijk et al., 2023) nor *in vivo* (Claussen et al., 2022; Sauvage et al., 1997), the confined, fluid-filled anatomy of the cochlea and its more restrained immune activity result in a highly sensitive electrode-tissue interface. As a result, even small biological or electrochemical changes can markedly influence impedance.

Sudden increases, fluctuations, or changes in electrode impedance have been associated with inflammatory events, reduction of CI performance, and residual hearing loss (Choi et al., 2017; Mussoi et al., 2024; Neuburger et al., 2009; Pitt et al., 2022; Saoji et al., 2022; Scherperle et al., 2017; Thompson et al., 2019). Electrical stimulation appears to interact with these processes. Previous studies have shown that stimulation can modify protein adsorption, reduce cellular adhesion, and alter the electrochemical behavior of the electrode surface (Aregueta-Robles et al., 2020; Newbold et al., 2004; Newbold et al., 2011). In our dataset, morning-to-evening impedance fluctuations emerged only after electrical stimulation began, suggesting that stimulation temporarily reorganizes the electrode-tissue interface in a way that lowers impedance during daily use. Several mechanisms could contribute to this effect. Electrical stimulation may alter the thin protein layer that forms on the electrode surface, making it less dense or more loosely organized and thereby improving conductivity. It may also influence how firmly macrophages and fibroblasts adhere to the electrode, leading to small, reversible changes in cellular coverage. In addition, stimulation may modify the local ionic environment and reduce polarization-related impedance components – a speculation supported by the observation that impedance often decreases within minutes of stimulation onset, both in our data and in previous reports.

When stimulation is paused overnight, these effects may partially revert – proteins may re-accumulate, cells may reattach more firmly, and electrochemical conditions return toward baseline – leading to the higher impedance values typically observed the following morning. We found evidence that these intra-day fluctuations can occur rapidly. One participant with exceptionally high compliance performed

measurements more than twice daily over several consecutive days (Supplementary Figure S5); in this case, impedance decreased from the morning peak within approximately 30 minutes after stimulation onset. A similar rapid decline has been described previously *in vivo* and correlated with the magnitude of impedance prior to stimulation (Newbold et al., 2014).

Experimental work further supports the idea that multiple mechanisms may contribute to these rapid fluctuations. *In vitro* studies have shown stimulation mediated reduction of polarization impedance by inhibition of protein-adsorption (Aregueta-Robles et al., 2020). On a clinical level, fluctuations have been attributed to change in polarization impedance as well (Saoji et al., 2025). In humans, adjustments to stimulation parameters can affect impedance levels (Neuburger et al., 2009), indicating that the interface responds dynamically to the electrical environment. Neuburger et al. further reported a temporal association between impedance increases and cochlear inflammation, including during episodes of common colds (Neuburger et al., 2009). Interestingly, temporary cessation of stimulation has been shown to reduce or stabilize elevated impedance in certain contexts (Saoji et al., 2025). Together, these findings suggest that electrical stimulation does not uniformly reduce impedance but can differentially influence the electrode–tissue interface depending on the underlying tissue state. In situations where the electrode–tissue interface is already affected by inflammation, ongoing stimulation may not alleviate, but exacerbate, impedance elevations, whereas temporary withdrawal of stimulation could allow partial recovery of the interface.

It is important to note that total impedance reflects a combination of biological and electrochemical components whose relative contributions may differ across users and over time (Pitt et al., 2022; Sanderson et al., 2019).

Because tissue encapsulation, protein deposition, and inflammatory reactions vary across individuals – and because impedance measurement techniques differ among manufacturers and studies (Caswell-Midwinter et al., 2022; Durisin et al., 2022; Li, 2023; Mussoi et al., 2024; Scheperle et al., 2017; Thompson et al., 2019) – a direct correlation between total impedance and the degree of fibrotic tissue is difficult to establish (Buswinka et al., 2022; Ishai et al., 2017; Sanderson et al., 2019).

4.5. Effects of dexamethasone on longitudinal impedance

In the DEX group, stable and low mean impedance values were observed throughout the study period. This was generally also the case for the individual user trajectories (Supplementary Figure S3). In those with higher initial levels (perhaps due to greater insertional trauma) impedance declined relatively rapidly to a low and stable steady state level. This pattern was also observed in one patient who underwent an extended round window approach (Supplementary Figure S3, DEX #04). Interestingly, a similar phenomenon was recently reported, suggesting that dexamethasone elution may temper trauma and inflammation arising from surgical-related events (Khan et al., 2026). In patients with immediate low impedance values, later levels stabilized on a slightly higher level. Slight variations in mean impedance values across different measurement days, but not within the same day, were observed in only two patients prior to the onset of electrical stimulation (Supplementary Figure S3, DEX #05 and DEX #07). The start of the intensive fitting phase revealed no clear effect on mean impedance values and no fluctuation between morning (3.20 ± 0.65 k Ω , $n = 8$) and evening (3.25 ± 0.63 k Ω , $n = 8$) levels could be seen. The inter-individual variance in impedance was also markedly lower among the DEX group (Figs. 1 B and 2 B), meaning that with DEX administration impedance levels are not just lower, but consistently so across users.

The reported findings of the DEX group are in strong contrast to the NoDEX group, in which impedance rises within the course post-inflammatory reactions and decrease as well as fluctuate with onset of stimulation. To ensure that the observed group differences were not

attributable to different perioperative baseline conditions, we additionally compared the clinically measured intraoperative impedances between DEX and NoDEX electrodes. This data showed no significant differences and is provided in Supplementary Figure S6. This observation aligns with findings by Khan et al., who reported that dexamethasone-eluting electrode arrays result in smaller and more stable impedance values across repeated measures during the first 90 days after initial activation compared with standard commercial arrays, while perioperative measurements showed comparable mean impedance values (Khan et al., 2026). Furthermore, the present study demonstrated that even before the onset of electrical stimulation, the DEX group exhibited lower impedance values and reduced variability compared with the NoDEX group.

In pre-clinical studies the effect of dexamethasone-elution on various stages of cochlear healing has been investigated. With dexamethasone-eluting electrodes, a decrease in the expression of various pro-inflammatory cytokines was observed, such as TNF- α and IL-1 β , during the initial pro-inflammatory phases (Takumi et al., 2014). Moreover, it stabilizes cochlear tissues by reducing influx of immune cells after cochlear implantation (Rahman et al., 2025).

The anti-inflammatory and anti-proliferative effects of dexamethasone have motivated its use in various implantable devices, including neural microelectrodes (Boehler et al., 2017), electrodes for peripheral nerve stimulation (Lee et al., 1993) and cardiac pacemakers (Mond et al., 2014; Radovsky et al., 1988), to reduce the foreign body response. In cochlear implantation, dexamethasone-eluting electrodes have been shown to reduce fibrous tissue formation and reduce electrode impedance (Bas et al., 2016; Briggs et al., 2020; Prenzler et al., 2025; Rahman et al., 2025; Wilk et al., 2016), while also attenuating inflammatory responses within the cochlea and improving tissue integrity during healing (Bas et al., 2015; Bas et al., 2016; MacArthur et al., 2015; Toulemonde et al., 2021).

In the absence of dexamethasone, the cochlear tissue response to implantation may be characterized not by a failure of the surgical wound to close, but by a less complete resolution of the early inflammatory and wound-healing processes. While the acute insertion trauma is expected to heal, the quality and organization of the resulting tissue interface may remain suboptimal, leaving it more susceptible to repeated activation by mechanical or electrical factors. In this scenario, the implanted electrode may continue to interact with a biologically reactive tissue environment, leading to ongoing protein turnover, cellular activity, and interface remodeling that remain detectable as impedance fluctuations, even long after implantation.

In contrast, dexamethasone administration during the early post-operative phase may promote a more controlled and resolved healing process, leading to a more organized repair response and a reduced degree of fibrotic scar formation (Schvartz-Leyzac et al., 2023), thereby contributing to a more stable and homogeneous electrode–tissue interface and reducing both immediate and delayed impairment of cochlear function. Once such an interface is established, subsequent electrical stimulation is less likely to provoke renewed biological responses, which could explain the sustained absence of intra-day impedance fluctuations observed in the DEX group, even years after implantation. This long-term stability is further supported by recent measures showing no daily impedance fluctuations over four years post-implantation (Supplementary Figure S7).

4.6. Future CI treatment

In this study we demonstrated that the dexamethasone-eluting FLEX28 electrode array achieves stable electrophysiological parameters within the early post-operative period and beyond. This, in turn, can be expected to yield more stable fitting parameters. Moreover, because early impedance fluctuations may influence initial fitting quality (Vormelcher et al., 2025), the greater stability observed with the DEX array is likely to be clinically beneficial during the initial fittings.

Combining this device with early processor activation (instead of the conventional one-month post-operative waiting period) may facilitate a stable and optimized fitting very early after implantation.

5. Conclusion

The use of the dexamethasone-eluting FLEX28 electrode array resulted in significantly lower daily impedance compared to the conventional FLEX28 electrode array. Importantly, no intra-day fluctuations between morning and evening impedance values were observed, indicating enhanced stability. These findings demonstrate that dexamethasone-eluting electrodes effectively reduce overall impedance levels and maintain consistent values over time. Our findings suggest that early modulation of cochlear wound healing may determine the long-term biological stability of the electrode-tissue interface, with lasting consequences for impedance behavior.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sarah Vormelcher: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maria Mitterberger-Vogt:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Nils Prenzler:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Cornelia Batsoulis:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Daniel Kley:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Thomas Lenarz:** Writing – review & editing. **Andreas Büchner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

Sarah Vormelcher, Maria Mitterberger-Vogt, and Cornelia Batsoulis report employment and financial support from MED-EL Medical Electronics GmbH. Daniel Kley reports funding grants and travel reimbursement from MED-EL Medical Electronics GmbH. All other authors declare no competing interests.

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Supplementary materials

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